

THE ROLE OF FAST SPEECH IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH

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Annotation: In this article, the importance of rapid pronunciation in the correct development of children's pronunciation is analyzed with the help of examples.

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How communication is formed in childhood reflects throughout a person's life.

It is an undeniable fact that the role of the family in the formation of a person as a person is an undeniable fact, as well as the development of his speech is a product of social conditions. "Social conditions", V. D. Bondaletov writes, "is the specific historical conditions in which the people live - that is, time". It always depends on the level of socio-economic, cultural and political development of the people".

For example, our great grandfather Alisher Navoi used 26,035 new words, and in this regard, he used many new words from prominent representatives of the world. The first reason why the poet achieved such a result is that he was born in the family of Giyaziddin, that is, in the family of a palace official, there were frequent meetings in his family, and young Alisher also participated in them. When we get acquainted with the poet's biography, he read and even memorized F. Attar's work "Mantiq-ut-tayr" when he was 4-5 years old, and at the end of his life he wrote "Lison-ut-tur" as a response to him.

we will witness what he wrote. Therefore, in the formation and development of a person's speech, the environment in which he lives and the created conditions are important . After all, the place and role of quick utterances in the formation of a young child's speech, like any building rising from the foundation, cannot be compared with anything.

Uzbek folklore, which is considered a priceless property of our people, has been living with our people since ancient times, passed from mouth to mouth. As an ancient verbal art, Uzbek folk art is distinguished not only by its deep idealism and high artistry, but also by its brightness of content and simplicity of language. Taking into account similar and different features of folklore, proverbs, riddles, epics, askiya, lof, anecdotes, etc. were formed, one of which is quick sayings. In ancient times, fast pronunciations are based on the fact that some speech sounds are repeated a lot or are placed in the structure of words and phrases in such a way that they are difficult to pronounce. "Rapid pronunciations help to pronounce a certain word, phrase or sound correctly, to distinguish it from other sounds, to develop speech, to increase the speed of reading, and at the same time to make large

numbers of digits. is a genre that teaches memory consolidation. According to the old rules, it was required to say fast in one breath”.

Effective use of prompts is of great importance in children's fluency. It is very important to improve the fluency of speech of students of school age and elementary grades. Because the role of fluency in speech is incomparable in ensuring the activity of children in our society based on the requirements of the present time. Because speech is a means of communication between people, it is the need of the hour to teach every young generation to master speech skills. Below we will focus on some rapid utterances that affect the fluency of speech.

The free farmer sows the early morning crop .

If we pay attention to this fast pronunciation, we will witness the repeated use of the vowel "e". It can be used to eliminate speech defects in children who have difficulty pronouncing the vowel "e". It is known that words beginning with the sound "e" are pronounced as "ye" in the speech of the population speaking the Kipchak dialect. This rapid pronunciation is effective for representatives of the Kipchak dialect, which is difficult to speak in the literary language.

Fast pronunciation is chosen depending on which vowels or consonants the child has difficulty pronouncing. For example:

Is Rukhsor angry with Rana?

Is Rano offended by Rukhsor?

Fast pronunciation is dedicated to the pronunciation of the consonant "R". We know that many children pronounce the sound "r" as "y" or "l". It's good to have children regularly practice these quick pronunciations.

Another sound that is difficult for young children to pronounce is the consonant "sh". In many cases, we witness that this sound is pronounced as "s". This, of course, will cause the speech to be confused, and even the meaning of some words to change. You can learn to pronounce this sound fully and fluently by saying the following quickly:

In the winter, the grapes are not ripe,

If it's ripe, it's not winter.

It is considered very difficult to say this quickly and it is difficult to repeat it in one breath. It is appropriate to diligently teach such rapid utterances to young children with speech defects.

Not only in children, but also in the speech of adults, the sounds "k" and "q" are mixed. This situation is especially common in the speech of representatives of the Oghuz

dialect. To learn to pronounce these sounds perfectly, it is effective to quickly say the following:

A blue lid on a white teapot,
Blue teapot with a white lid.

In general, the importance of rapid speech in speech development is incomparable. The formation of a child's speech ability is one of the problems that has never lost its relevance. Because if children develop in all aspects, the society will also flourish.

